

MANAGERIAL PERCEPTION OF OPEN INNOVATION AS A POST COVID OPPORTUNITY

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Abstract

Purpose – This study explores the industry managers' perception of open innovations, potential benefits, and expected barriers when adopting the open innovation concept.

Methodology/approach - We used a qualitative approach by interviewing 13 managers and investigating case studies. We concluded that applications of open innovation attract more research.

Findings – Case studies describing the best practice and the most common barriers to participation in an innovation network are necessary to understand the field better. In addition, we find out that exploring and understanding the managerial perception of open innovation and how this concept appears on the public agenda is necessary.

Research limitations/implications – Some limitations due to methodological aspects, issues regarding research samples and the techniques for collecting the data.

Practical implications – Through exploratory research, we aim to identify the managerial perception of the concept of open innovation. Regarding the manager's role in dealing with this kind of innovation, we are interested in whether open innovation is associated with leadership characteristics.

Originality/value – This study addresses the concept of open innovation, that hasn't been applied in the industry and is quite controversial in the literature. In the past decade, research on open innovation has brought renewed attention to the ways in which companies can gain from interactions with external sources of knowledge and innovation.

Key words: Innovation, Manager, SMEs

1. Introduction

To be competitive and successful in an ever-changing business environment and in a dynamic market, companies need to innovate. In innovation strategy there are different degrees of openness to the external environment. Three types of innovation strategies are identified: open, semi-open and closed. Open innovators are those who primarily use open source in their innovation projects, while the semi-open ones don't use external sources unless in less important phases of open innovation process, opening it depends on the absorption of the company and the need for external knowledge (Barge-Gil, 2010). Implementation of open innovation requires a change in mindset and a change in organizational culture. It requires openness to the ideas of others and the desire to share knowledge. This requires a new vision to the way innovation is traditionally understood.

After only a decade after its appearance in literature, the concept of open innovation has grown into a thriving area of research in innovation management. Increased interest in open innovation is manifested by the rapid growth of scientific publications on this concept and the frequency with which the concept appears as a theme in management journals.

Open innovation, as a term, was promoted by professor and executive director of the Center for Open Innovation at the University of California, Berkley, Henry Chesbrough as a response to recent technological advances and significant changes in the business environment. This concept refers to the user's innovation, cumulative innovation, trade of knowledge, mass innovation and distributed innovation, "open innovation is a model that assumes that firms can and should use external ideas as well as internal ideas, and internal and external paths towards the market, as the firms are turning towards technological advance "(Chesbrough, 2003). Or, as defined by Stephan Lidegaard (2011): "Open innovation is about creating a link between internal and external resources and acting with these opportunities" (Chesbrough and Bogers, 2014).

One particular area which is becoming more and more important in open innovation is the development of collaborative innovation that combines the inputs and output of knowledge. As association process, collaborative innovation combines inputs and outputs, allowing associated organizations to develop and to put joint innovation in the market.

Of course, as it spread, the concept of open innovation also attracted criticism. Dahlander and Gann (2010) note that although in existing research there are various definitions and points of interest, it lacks a coherent analytical framework. The authors pointed out that the lack of this analytical framework makes it difficult to compare and validate the results reported in open organization.

The pandemic produced a series of challenges for businesses in all countries and they had to act quickly and decisively. In the recovery stage after the pandemic, companies should identify and benefit from the new opportunities that have appeared. But for this it is necessary to take into account the lessons learned during the pandemic, that is, to make certain evaluations after the action. Companies will have to prioritize their actions and strengthen their strategic resistance. Thus, they will be able to benefit better from the opportunities that appear in the post-pandemic period.

In terms of innovation for development, there have been a number of programs with real gains on a large scale. They include: using mobile money and microfinance to boost financial inclusion and small business development, then reducing costs and facilitating access to medicines in low-income areas. All this involves a series of technical problems related to innovation, but also business planning problems (Ramalingam and Prabhu, 2020).

This study explores the industry managers' perception of open innovations, potential benefits, and expected barriers when adopting the open innovation concept.

The rest of the paper is structured into four sections. The next section reviews the relevant literature in the field of innovation, while the last three sections would provide the methodology, the research approach of the study, and conclusions.

2. Literature review

It is considered that at present the need for innovation is very high, even urgent, as it greatly influences the social well-being and economic development of a country.

Incentives for innovation, investment and education are crucial and institutions need to provide a framework for these incentives (Kramer, 2016). It is up to governments to find the most effective ways to act, but they must be correlated with the specifics of each country.

Many industrialized countries, to increase efficiency, place the company at the center of the strategies they adopt. Therefore, those policies will be designed to support the development of small businesses and start-ups, providing support for the entire life cycle of new products (Sadeh, 2013), from design to internationalization. Very important in this sense are the business incubators, they ensure an important role in the survival rate of young companies.

Moreover, for all countries, including those in Eastern Europe, it is important to keep in mind that production capacity does not automatically lead to innovation capacity. Overall, Eastern European countries are inefficient both in converting their research, development and innovation capacities to appropriate levels of productivity and in transforming research and development capacities into results such as resident patents, etc. (Kravtsova and Radosevic, 2012).

Regarding Romania, it is considered that public and private investment in infrastructure, education, healthcare, social inclusion, and innovation could improve productivity and growth in the long term. At the same time, Romania's modest performance in the field of research and innovation limits growth prospects, and the overall innovative capacity of the economy remains low.

For a country to have a competitive economy, it is very important to produce applied knowledge itself. This is because the application of innovation in the economy brings benefits to everyone, including for those who do not innovate or work in innovative sectors. As for Romania, it should also learn from the experience of other countries that have developed innovative areas and that allow for sustainable development (Pop, 2014).

Ihl et al. (2012) showed that structural dimensions, such as specialization, formalization and decentralization, affect the gains from open innovation. Also, it appears that R&D-intensive firms do not make additional gains from open innovation, while low-R&D firms can successfully replace their own internal R&D, at least to some degree of openness (Naqshbandi and Kamel, 2017).

It is possible that the paradigm shifts caused by the pandemic will have far-reaching long-term effects. Organizations should pay attention to the new consumption trends, while identifying the measures that can be taken to protect their financial integrity and the ability to operate profitably. Certain industries such as: entertainment, sports, airlines, restaurants, etc. are forced to find new ways of action and opportunities to be profitable in the new business environment (Howe et al., 2021).

Howe et al. (2021) pointed out that a mentality that tries to aggressively return all work activities back to normal could have a negative impact, with harmful results on the performance and turnover of companies.

Ramalingam and Prabhu (2020) talked about the need to reset the economic system and ensure an "ecological recovery" in the post-pandemic period. This implies policy innovations, but also related organizational and technological innovations.

3. Methodology

To achieve the study's objectives of the study, we conducted qualitative interviews with managers of SMEs who participated in such projects. We chose this exploratory investigation method because it is suitable for new themes, is little researched, and doesn't have a very solid theoretical foundation as open innovation. We selected 13 industrial companies from Romania that, according to previous research (Dimensions Innovation in terms of change management), said that conducted open innovation. Out of these, 7 agreed to participate in the study. The fields of activities of the participating companies are textiles, furniture industry, aluminum joinery and metal constructions. They have 11 to 294 employees and have been in the business from 11 to 23 years.

We collected data through interviews with managers or directors of these companies based on semi-structured guides. The questions refer to the perception of managers on the obstacles and benefits of the projects of open innovation, the employees' motivation in such projects and the essential elements of such an approach.

4. Results and discussion

We aimed to identify the managerial perception of the concept of open innovation and the appearances of online business media on this concept. Regarding the manager's role in dealing with this kind of innovation, we are interested in whether open innovation is associated with leadership characteristics. It is an empirical study on a topic that is currently very little research. We'll find out what managers think about open innovation. The research objective was to find out the perception of managers about open innovation, specifically the benefits and obstacles perceived by those who have undertaken such projects.

The data was collected through interviews with managers or directors of these companies based on semi-structured guides. The questions refer to the perception of managers on the obstacles and benefits of the projects of open innovation, the employees' motivation in such projects and the essential elements of such an approach.

The main barriers identified by managers in implementing open innovation are:

- Lack of familiarity with the concept.
- Reluctance of companies facing such projects.
- Concerns with Intellectual Properties by potential partners.

The main benefits that managers think that open innovation brings to a company are:

- It offers a fresh perspective on their projects
- It reduces innovation risk.
- It reduces costs.

In small and medium businesses, innovation becomes a strategy when the product is a generic and when differentiation from the competition is made by the price alone. Such a strategy is needed more than ever because of the technological complexity of shortening the product's life cycle. Thus, to differentiate and create value in a market that puts pressure on existing products, firms choose innovation as their business strategy. Although the interviewed companies do not use very high technology (due to their domain), the technological process has an important role in innovation strategy because it is a way to create value for the end consumer, which translates into economic value of the product. Unlike large companies that have resources at hand for in-depth analysis of market trends or to test latest technologies, in the case of SMEs, the manager/business owner is the one that most often establishes, based on his personal beliefs and his vision on market developments, the company's innovation strategy. Two of the managers believe that open innovation is not an option, but a requirement given that SMEs do not have the skills and financial resources needed to develop the technology on their own.

The most common notional categories associated with the concept of open innovation found in the transcript of the answers are "partnership", "partner", "complementary", "contact", "external environment". In the "partner" category: „clients“, „consumers“, „firms in the same field“ and „researchers“ were included.

After analyzing the answers received from the managers, we identified several key elements of an open innovation project.

Fig.1. Aspects of open innovation
Source: Authors' computations

The vision. Most of the time, a manager's new vision is the start of a new business mode. This vision must be based on experience and a good knowledge of the domain in which the company operates.

Partners. Open innovation involves a network of external partners, which might be companies in the same field, research centers or universities. Partners are identified depending on technology, skills and market position. The size of the network depends on the products or services that are sought to be done.

Managing relationships with partners is an important aspect of open business models. This should be considered the making of common value and the distribution of this amount between partners. Sometimes, there are tensions but partners must always be aware that common values are greater than that which could be achieved by each on their own. Unless open network partners perceive benefits as greater than those of a classic innovation strategy is the network sustainable and can achieve its goals. Building strong relationships based on trust and transparency is essential to cope with market risks. Personal relationships between the involved parties are also important.

Projects' evolution. An open innovation project does not end with the launch of a new product, it is just the beginning. The involved companies acquire new skills and thus become more competent, more profitable and such initiatives always generate new opportunities. On the other hand, the market is very dynamic and new products can be taken over in a relatively short time and new strategies always must be taken into consideration.

SMEs' competitiveness doesn't only depend on the employees' skills but also relational capital the company has, as it strengthens the bargaining position and makes the company alert to the other companies in the same area.

One of the questions for managers refers to the necessary qualities for a manager to successfully start and run open innovation projects. This analysis answers one of the questions of the study, namely, whether the managers' perception of the necessary qualities for open innovation coincide with those of a leader. The common characteristics of these two identified dimensions in the answers received are: openness to the new, the existence of a strategy, the ability to manage relationships within a team (in and outside the organization), including conflict management, risk taking and knowledge sharing.

Fig. 2. Qualities necessary for the initiation and development of open innovation projects
Source: Authors' computations

An important aspect of an open innovation project is the intellectual property. For a better management there is the need to clearly define each involved member's commitment. Development of common knowledge can be protected by certifications, trademarks, patents and licenses. In the case of the companies surveyed the managers say they don't choose co-patenting, but they prefer to establish through contracts the rights of use of the inventions made. This can cause problems and tensions, but it's important that partners remain focus on the value created and to ensure transparency in their activities on joint projects.

The press and other media mean *par excellence* vehicles that help to build the image of an event, a phenomenon or a new trend and accredit it as such in public space, justifying the scientific approach to communication. We tried to identify if the concept of open innovation appears in the press of online

business. The results were surprising. This concept only appears in few isolated business articles. For data selection we used intentional selection, guided by aiming at research, named *theoretical sampling*. Since the proposed topic is well-defined, data selection meant choosing media sources having published articles about it. The concept was found only on the following sites: <http://incomemagazine.ro/> sites, with two articles published on the subject in 2009 (*SMEs and innovation management*) and in 2012 „*Geniuses: solitary or collaborative? Where does innovation in business come from?*”, <http://www.businessmagazin.ro/> with the article „*integration of the Lego brick in the digital era*” published in 2014 and <http://www.revistabiz.ro/> with the articles „*leaders after the 2011 crisis*” and „*how competitive is Romania?*” in 2014.

Conclusions

A common aspect of the answers received from the managers surveyed is focusing the company's efforts on creating value for a certain category of customers. They start with a coherent idea about a customers' need, about the one thing which the customer assigns value.

This begins innovation in an existing business model. Sometimes the new business model is simple, and sometimes it is shaped by a complex process that can take months and is followed by decisions on what technologies will be used and the potential partners.

Although an open innovation project is emergent, it changes over time, discoveries and adjustments are made, and it should have a complete business plan. When firms innovate, they increase the functionality of a product, make it more affordable for the customer (in terms of use), add a service to an existing product, or offer customers new experiences. The latter is difficult to accomplish but always proves profitable in the long-term and significantly improves the company's market position.

The changes that make innovation needed are usually the emergence of new competitors, changes in legislation, technological developments, changes in the consumer's behavior: new expectations concerning the company's social responsibility or environmental impact. The change category especially offers opportunities for sustainable innovation and brings measurable results in the company's profitability. The benefits compared to large companies are agility, dynamism, and the ability to specialization for services/customized products. SMEs also exploit the opportunities offered by smaller markets which are of no interest to large companies.

The concept of open innovation should be investigated in more detail. Case studies describing both best practice and the most common barriers to participating in an innovation network are absolutely necessary to better understand the field. In addition, we consider it is necessary to explore and understand the managerial perception of open innovation, the mode of organization, and how the manager communicates innovation among his employees.

By its very nature, innovation involves taking risks, oscillating between successes and failures. In the context of the pandemic, health-focused innovations are the most visible forms of innovation. We then talk about many innovations that address the indirect or secondary impact of the pandemic, including: public policy measures taken to help businesses hit hard by the pandemic, innovations to strengthen social solidarity, and organizational innovations to deal with lockdowns (e.g., increasing methods of online work) (Ramalingam and Prabhu, 2020).

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